

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№3(2)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 170 sahifa,
16-mart, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

- Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalarini tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the Editorial Board of the newspapers "Yangi Uzbekiston" and "Pravda Vostoka", Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Philological Sciences (PhD)

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Katta guruh tarbiyalanuvchilarida kasb haqidagi dastlabki tasavvurlarni shakllantirish metodikasini innovatsion ekotizim sharoitida takomillashtirish	18
Uralova Fotima Baxtiyor qizi	
Malakali sportchilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirishda sotsiologik yondashuv (gandbolchilar misolida).....	23
G. A. Valiyeva	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida motor alaliyali bolalarni ruhiy va nutqiy rivojlantirish usullari	27
Suyunova Surayyo Ulash qizi	
Sog'lom bola ekotizimining asoslari: ovqatlanish, immunitet va rivojlanish	31
Israilova Xusnida Adilovna	
Mobil ilovalar yordamida mustaqil o'qishni rivojlantirish	37
Raximova Feruza Najmiddinovna	
Biologiya darslarida muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasini qo'llash orqali mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	42
Dauekeeva Gulistan Orinbaevna	
Talabalarga ingliz tilidagi matnlarni kommunikativ metod yordamida o'qish texnikasini takomillashtirish usullari	46
Mo'minova Mahliyo Axrorjonovna	
Velosiped haydashning afzalliklari.....	49
Raxmonova Go'zal Bobir qizi	
Компетентностный подход как стратегическая основа модернизации образования и его реализация в преподавании русского языка как иностранного в Узбекистане	54
Мирзакбарова Севда Вахиддиновна	
Umumta'lim maktablarida texnologiya fani mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari va metodlari.....	58
Ziyamova Gulbaxor Tulabayevna	
Типы аббревиации в русском и узбекском языках: сравнительно-типологический анализ.....	62
Рахмонова Бахтигул Пайзилловна	
Maktabgacha ta'limda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonida didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish metodikasi	65
Abidjonova Mushtariybonu Qobiljon qizi	
Tarbiyaviy tadbirlarni samarali tashkil etishda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalarning o'zaro hamkorlik masalalari.....	71
Sanayeva Surayyo Bobonazarovna, Jabborova Shaxina G'affor qizi	
Qadriyatli yondashuv asosida talabalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish ..	76
G'aybullayev Quvonchbek G'olibovich	
Maktab o'quvchilarida stressga barqarorlik namoyon bo'lishining psixologik tahlili	83
Ismoilova N. Z.	
Yoshlar ma'naviyatini shakllantirishda milliy qadriyatlarning o'rni.....	87
Karshiyev Jaxongir Abdirayimovich	
Funksional savodxonlikni rivojlantirishda o'qish savodxonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	91
Xatamova Munisa Mamadulla qizi	
Transformatsiyalash tizimi asosida o'quvchilarning loyihalash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish samaradorligi.....	95
Jurayeva Zulayxo Islomovna	
Zamonaviy boshqaruv nazariyalarida rahbar muloqoti (transformatsion, kommunikativ va ishtirokchi boshqaruv yondashuvlari asosida).....	102
Islamova Dिल्фуза Dilshodovna	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida pedagogik kompetentlikni tabaqalashgan yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish mazmuni	107
Begmatova Nasiba Mengnarovna	
Bo'lajak maxsus pedagoglarni inklyuziv ta'limda subyektlar faoliyatini o'rgatish metodikasi	112
Dilshodov Abrorjon Dilshodjon o'g'li	
Pre-Reading Activities to Enhance Foreign Language Reading Comprehension: Reading "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer" in 10–11 Grades	118
Djumaniyazova Zulfiya Kaliyevna	
Nutq aktlarini o'rgatishda autentik materiallardan foydalanishning metodik imkoniyatlari (filologik yo'nalish talabalari misolida)	122
Fayzulloeva Chevar G'ayrat qizi	
Yangi O'zbekistonda talaba-yoshlarni milliy yuksaltirishda jadid-marifatparvarlari ilgari surgan g'oyalarning o'rni va roli	125
Mamadaliyev Abduvoxid Maxsitaliyevich	
Gimnastikaning O'zbekistonga kirib kelish va rivojlanish tarixi	128
N. Q. Mamasidova	
Uglevodorodlar tarkibini aniqlashda massa ulushiga asoslangan reflektiv yondashuv (7-9-sinflar misolida)	131
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich, Smanova Zulayxo Asanalievna	
Screencasting materiallarini yaratish va ularni o'quv jarayonida qo'llash	134
Maxmudova Dilfuza Meliyevna, Ergashov Niyozxon Ilyozxon o'g'li	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda so'z shakllanishini psixolingvistik asoslari	137
Moxirabonu G'aniyeva Adxam qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'limdagi muammolar va yechimlar: o'zbekiston respublikasi tajribasi	140
N. Sh. Miryusupova	
Interaktiv kartografik resurslar va ularning ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishining didaktik, kognitiv hamda metodik asoslari	143
Olimova Aziza Abdullayevna	
Mentorlik tizimining tarixiy ildizlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	147
Oxunova Dilnoza Qaxxorjonovna, Abdumannonova Durdonaxon Shuxratjon qizi	
Talabalarning psixologik holati va stress omillarining prokrastinatsiyaga ta'siri hamda mustaqil ta'lim faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash usullari	150
Razakov Farxod Kuvondikovich, Rajabov Hikmat Toshevich	
Talabalarni stulda o'tirgan qiyofachi portreti ranglavhasini ishlashga o'rgatish metodikasi	154
Sadatov Chori Xolmuradovich	
Organik kimyo fanini o'qitishda teskari ta'lim va texnologiyalarning ahamiyati	158
Umrbekova Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna, Abdulkakimova Gulziyba Ziyatdinovna	
Duduqlanishni bartaraf etishda kompleks metodlarini qo'llashning samaradorligi	162
Xasanova Barnoxon Abdusattor qizi	
Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kompetentligini takomillashtirish	165
Xolbozorova Nasiba Xolbozar qizi	
Проектирование персонализированных образовательных сценариев в дошкольном образовании средствами генеративного искусственного интеллекта	168
Пак Диана Александровна	

PRE-READING ACTIVITIES TO ENHANCE FOREIGN LANGUAGE READING COMPREHENSION: READING “THE ADVENTURES OF TOM SAWYER” IN 10–11 GRADES

Djumaniyazova Zulfiya Kaliyevna

PhD student at the department of english language and literature
Karakalpak state university

Abstract: This article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations of pre-reading activities in teaching foreign language reading to students of grades 10-11, focusing on the literary work “The Adventures of Tom Sawyer” by Mark Twain. Pre-reading tasks are analyzed in terms of their role in activating students’ background knowledge, reducing cognitive load, and improving reading comprehension. The article also provides practical examples of pre-reading exercises for literary texts, demonstrating how students can engage with new vocabulary, predict the development of the storyline, and understand the cultural context. The results of the study highlight the effectiveness of pre-reading activities in enhancing students’ reading skills and their overall communicative competence.

Key words: foreign language reading, pre-reading activities, literary text, cognitive load, prediction strategies, multilingual education.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada 10-11-sinf o’quvchilariga chet tilida o’qish ko’nikmalarini o’rgatishda pre-reading (matni o’qishdan oldingi) faoliyatlarning nazariy va metodik asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot Mark Tvenning “Tom Soyerning sarguzashtlari” asari misolida badiiy matn bilan ishlash jarayoniga qaratilgan. Pre-reading topshiriqlari o’quvchilarning oldindan mavjud bilimlarini faollashtirish, kognitiv yuklamani kamaytirish hamda matnni tushunishni yaxshilashdagi roli nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, badiiy matnlar bilan ishlash jarayonida qo’llash mumkin bo’lgan amaliy pre-reading mashqlari misollari keltiriladi. Ushbu mashqlar orqali o’quvchilar yangi so’zlarni o’zlashtirish, voqealar rivojini oldindan taxmin qilish va madaniy kontekstni anglash jarayoniga faol jalb etilishi ko’rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so’zlar: chet tilida o’qish, pre-reading faoliyatlar, badiiy matn, kognitiv yuklama, taxmin qilish strategiyalari, ko’p tilli ta’lim.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические и методические основы использования предтекстовых заданий при обучении чтению на иностранном языке учащихся 10-11-х классов на материале художественного произведения Марка Твена “Приключения Тома Сойера”. Анализируется роль предтекстовых заданий в активизации фоновых знаний учащихся, снижении когнитивной нагрузки и повышении уровня понимания текста. Приводятся практические примеры предтекстовых упражнений для работы с художественными текстами, демонстрирующие, как учащиеся могут взаимодействовать с новой лексикой, прогнозировать развитие сюжета и осмысливать культурный контекст.

Ключевые слова: чтение на иностранном языке, предтекстовые задания, художественный текст, когнитивная нагрузка, стратегии прогнозирования, многоязычное образование.

INTRODUCTION

Reading literary texts in a foreign language exposes students to authentic language, idiomatic expressions, stylistic devices, and culturally embedded meanings that are rarely encountered in standard textbooks ^[1]. Unlike adapted instructional materials, literary works present language in its natural communicative and artistic form, thereby contributing to the development of linguistic, sociocultural, and pragmatic competence. In grades 10-11, students are expected to demonstrate advanced reading skills, including the ability to comprehend complex narratives, analyze character development, identify implicit meanings, and interpret thematic content. At this stage of education, reading literature contributes not only to vocabulary expansion and grammatical awareness but also to the formation of critical and creative thinking skills ^[2].

Literary analysis encourages learners to reflect, compare perspectives, and formulate personal interpretations, which are essential components of higher-order cognitive development. However, reading authentic

literary texts in a foreign language presents significant challenges. Students may encounter unfamiliar vocabulary, historical and cultural references, figurative language, and non-standard syntactic structures. These difficulties can lead to increased cognitive load and reduced motivation, especially in multilingual educational contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In Karakalpak schools, English is studied within a multilingual environment where students use Karakalpak, Uzbek, and Russian as languages of communication and instruction. Such linguistic diversity, while enriching, may intensify cross-linguistic interference and complicate comprehension processes [6: 8]. Learners must simultaneously manage multiple linguistic systems, which can affect reading fluency and depth of understanding. For this reason, pre-reading activities play a crucial methodological role in foreign language instruction. They prepare students cognitively, linguistically, and culturally before engaging with a literary text.

Through vocabulary scaffolding, background knowledge activation, prediction tasks, and thematic discussions, pre-reading activities reduce comprehension barriers and promote meaningful interaction with the text. Thus, the integration of structured pre-reading strategies is particularly important in multilingual classrooms, where effective scaffolding can significantly enhance students' reading comprehension and engagement with literary works. Pre-reading tasks positioned before encountering the text serve several pedagogical functions [1: 3]:

- activation of prior knowledge;
- introduction of key vocabulary and thematic concepts;
- motivation for reading;
- development of prediction strategies and inferencing skills.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to schema theory, comprehension improves when students activate relevant cognitive schemata before reading a text [5]. Grabe and Stoller emphasize that pre-teaching vocabulary and thematic content significantly improves global and detailed comprehension [4]. Research also shows that pre-reading activities reduce cognitive load in multilingual contexts, compensating for potential interference from the first language [6]. Pre-Reading Activities for *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*. The following section provides practical examples of pre-reading tasks for grade 10-11 students, structured around cognitive, predictive, and cultural engagement strategies.

Cognitive tasks.

Task 1: Vocabulary Activation. Students review and discuss key words and phrases: river, raft, adventure, mischief, town, school, punishment, friendship, childhood, pranks.

Task 2: Word Prediction. Look at an illustration of Tom and Huck by the Mississippi River. What do you think they are planning? Write three sentences predicting the adventure.

Task 3: Concept Discussion. Students discuss key concepts such as friendship, childhood, morality, and rule-breaking. This prepares them to recognize important ideas and relationships in the text. Predictive tasks.

Task 4: Title and Chapter Prediction. Chapter title: "Tom and Becky's Adventure." Discussion prompts: What might happen to Tom and Becky? Will they encounter danger? How might their friendship influence the events?

Table 1: Event Prediction Table

Predicted Event	Checked After Reading
Tom will play a prank	Yes / No
Becky will get lost	Yes / No
They will escape danger	Yes / No

This allows students to engage in top-down processing, forming hypotheses that are later confirmed or revised. Sociocultural tasks such as cultural and personal reflection further deepen students' engagement with the text. Discussion questions may include how Tom's childhood compares to the students' own experiences. In this activity, students analyze aspects such as freedom and responsibilities, school life, family relationships, and leisure activities.

Another discussion question encourages students to consider how they would respond in similar situations. For example, they reflect on whether they would whitewash the fence as Tom did, whether they would tell the truth in difficult situations, and how they would react to peer pressure. These tasks encourage students to connect personally and culturally with the text, which increases both comprehension and motivation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Indicate that pre-reading activities constitute a crucial methodological component in teaching foreign-language literary texts in upper-secondary classrooms. When carefully structured, these activities function as cognitive scaffolding that supports learners before they engage with complex authentic material such as *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer* by Mark Twain. Literary texts in a foreign language often contain unfamiliar vocabulary, historical references, and culturally specific expressions. Without preparatory support, students may experience cognitive overload, which can negatively affect comprehension and motivation. Pre-teaching key vocabulary and essential concepts reduces extraneous cognitive load and allows learners to focus on meaning construction rather than word-by-word decoding.

Activities may include semantic mapping of thematic vocabulary such as childhood, superstition, and social norms; context-based guessing exercises; matching tasks or short lexical quizzes; and visual vocabulary prompts. By clarifying potentially problematic lexical items in advance, teachers create conditions for more fluent and confident reading. Effective reading involves interaction between bottom-up decoding and top-down processing. Pre-reading activities such as prediction tasks, brainstorming, and hypothesis formation activate learners' prior knowledge, often referred to as schema, and encourage anticipatory thinking. Typical tasks include title and cover analysis, predicting plot development based on chapter headings, generating hypotheses about characters, and completing exercises such as "What do you expect will happen next?". These activities stimulate top-down strategies by encouraging students to form expectations before reading.

As a result, learners approach the text with a clear purpose and are better prepared to interpret meaning beyond literal comprehension. Literary texts are embedded within specific historical and cultural contexts, and for contemporary multilingual classrooms the socio-cultural background of nineteenth-century America may be unfamiliar. Pre-reading tasks that introduce cultural elements therefore help bridge this gap and enable students to interpret the narrative more effectively within its historical and social framework.

Picture 1: Examples of culturally oriented pre-reading activities

Mini-presentations on life along the Mississippi River Discussion of childhood in the 19th century versus today o Analysis of illustrations depicting small-town American life of Reflection on moral values and social norms of the period Such tasks foster intercultural awareness and invite students to compare their own experiences with those represented in the literary text. This process encourages both personal engagement and critical thinking. Motivation plays a central role in successful foreign-language reading. Pre-reading activities can significantly increase engagement by connecting thematic content to students' interests and developmental stages. Themes in *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*—friendship, rebellion, adventure, and identity formation—resonate strongly with adolescents in grades 10-11. When teachers initiate discussions on topics such as: "Why do teenagers challenge authority?" "What does freedom mean to young people?" "Is mischief always negative?" students develop emotional involvement before encountering the text itself. Interactive pre-reading

formats (group discussions, visual prompts, and role-play preparation) further enhance participation and reduce anxiety, particularly among less confident learners.

In multilingual educational settings, students often possess varying proficiency levels and diverse cultural backgrounds. Pre-reading activities function as inclusive pedagogical tools that: of provide linguistic scaffolding for weaker learners of activate diverse cultural perspectives o encourage collaborative meaning-making of reduce comprehension anxiety. By bridging linguistic and cultural gaps, these tasks allow students to approach literary texts not as inaccessible artifacts but as meaningful communicative experiences. Methodologically, pre-reading activities are not merely introductory exercises; they represent strategic instructional interventions grounded in cognitive, linguistic, and sociocultural theory. When integrated systematically, they enhance comprehension, foster intercultural competence, and increase learner motivation—particularly in the context of teaching foreign-language literary works in upper-secondary education.

CONCLUSION

Pre-reading activities are a vital component of teaching foreign-language reading in grades 10-11. In the context of *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*, these tasks activate prior knowledge; introduce essential vocabulary and concepts; develop prediction and inferencing skills; and encourage cultural and personal engagement. By applying pre-reading strategies, teachers can enhance comprehension, critical thinking, and motivation when working with foreign-language literary texts in multilingual educational environments.

References:

1. Galskova, N.D. *Theory of Foreign Language Teaching*. Moscow, 2018.
2. Zimnya, I.A. *Psychology of Foreign Language Learning*. Moscow, 2015.
3. Solovova, E.N. *Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages*. Moscow, 2017.
4. Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. *Teaching and Researching Reading*. London, 2013.
5. Anderson, N.J. *Exploring Second Language Reading*. Boston, 2009.
6. Jalalov, J.D. *Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages*. Tashkent, 2012.
7. Ishmukhamedov, R.J. *Innovative Technologies in Education*. Tashkent, 2016.
8. Allambergenova, G.K. *Issues of Multilingual Education*. Nukus, 2019.
9. Pirnazarov, A.U. *Teaching Foreign Languages in Karakalpak Schools*. Nukus, 2017.
10. Khasanboev, Zh. *Pedagogy*. Tashkent, 2010.
11. Otamurodova, F.E. The Effects of Pre-Reading Activities on ESP Reading Comprehension. – *International Journal of European Research Output*, Vol. 3, No. 3, 2024.
12. Zarfsaz, E., & Yeganehpour, P. The Effect of Timing of Pre-Reading Activities on High Intermediate EFL Learners' Reading Comprehension. – *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 2025.
13. Jimenez, C.D., & Velasco, C.Q. Pre-Reading Activities and Reading Comprehension in an ESL Classroom. – *IJSSHM Research*, 2023.
14. Irawan, L.A., & Ahmad, R. Reading Comprehension and Test-Taking Strategies of Different Achievement Levels. – *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 2024.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №3(2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.